

Effect of Skin wrinkles on production traits in sheep: An overview

Mubashir Ali Rather, Showkat A Ahanger

¹ Sheep Husbandry Department, Faculty of Veterinary sciences and Animal Husbandry,
Shuhama, Aulestang, SKUAST-Kashmir, 190006

Corresponding Author: mubashir.70011@gmail.com

Abstract

Sheep farmers in valley have started breeding sheep for high density of skin folds. The trait has negative impact on production and reproduction traits of sheep. The sheep carrying ribs, folds or pleats are called wrinkly, developed or pleated sheep whereas sheep free of these ribs or wrinkles are called plain-bodied or flat-skinned. Higher skin folds have negative impact on wool and mutton traits. The practice of breeding sheep for ribs needs to be discouraged. The lambs with high degree of skin folds should be castrated at earlier age. Farmers should be encouraged and trained to bred sheep for fast growth rate. Animal breeds having higher skin mass will result in lesser carcass yield and dressing percentage. Lambs with more wrinkles tend to exhibit worse scarring from shearing and processing damage of pelts from the slaughter process. The more wrinkled animals produce more grease wool of undesirable staple length and fibre diameter. The sheep carrying ribs or folds have slow growth rate, lower lambing and weaning percentage. Therefore, it is concluded that breeding Kashmir Merino for skin wrinkles will dilute and deteriorate all production and reproduction traits. Higher skin fold has negative impact on wool, mutton, reproduction and carcass traits. The practice of breeding sheep for skin folds should be discouraged.

Introduction

Wrinkles are the raised folds on the skin of sheep in particular Merinos and related breeds. The raised folds on the skin are called as ribs, folds or pleats (Scobie et al. 2005). The sheep carrying these ribs are called wrinkly, developed or pleated sheep whereas sheep free of these ribs or wrinkles are called plain-bodied or flat-skinned (Scobie et al. 2005). Kashmir Merino is a highly variable (Dixit et al., 2006) synthetic and predominant sheep found in every nook and corner of Kashmir valley (Rather. 2019). As the sheep is highly variable in morphological and production traits (Dixit et al., 2006) due to involvement of number of native and exotic breeds in its evolution the breed exhibits varying degree of skin wrinkle. During last few years a trend has emerged among

sheep farmers towards breeding sheep for high degree of skin pleats. Despite the trait (high degree of skin folds) has negative impact on production and reproduction traits the farmers and breeders prefer wrinkly sheep over plain-bodied or flat-skinned. The present article is written to highlight the effect of skin wrinkles on some economic traits of sheep.

Leather quality: Sheep having numerous ribs may produce low quality leather (Holst et al. 1997). The pelts of Australian Merino lambs carry more wrinkles tend to exhibit worse scarring from shearing and more processing damage from the slaughter process than crossbred lamb pelts (Holst et al. 1997).

Shearing time: More time is required for shearing wrinkly sheep than flat-skinned sheep.

Fleece weight: Weight of each fleece as it is shorn is fleece weight or greasy fleece weight as it includes dirt and grease along with wool. However, it is desirable to have clean wool yield which is seldom estimated except under experimental conditions. It was believed in past sheep with more wrinkles provide more surface area for wool growth, therefore, produce more wool. However, it is proved that sheep with increased number and size of skin folds produce more greasy wool containing high amount of grease, dirt, moisture, etc (Scobie et al., 2005). Further, greater shrinkage has been reported in the fleece from wrinkled sheep (Milton., et al. 1943). Therefore, it is concluded that there is not much difference in clean wool yield although sheep with wrinkled skin produce more greasy wool. Further, wool has lost its market due and there is a shift in objective of sheep farming from wool to mutton traits (Rather. 2019). The more wrinkled animals produce more greasy wool, but this will not benefit if wool is sold on the basis of its actual value as predicted by actual shrinkage tests (Milton., et al. 1943).

Fibre diameter and staple length: Scobie et al. (2005) reported fibre diameter of wool in smooth Merino and smooth crossbred sheep was 0.1 μ and 0.4 μ finer than that of wrinkly types. Wool from the smoother bodied type is equally fine, and the fineness tends to be more uniform (Milton., et al. 1943). Milton et al. (1943) have reported that wool on folds tends to be coarser than that in adjacent areas and staple length tends to be greater on the smooth bodied type. Scobie et al. (2005) reported wool of higher staple length (55.7 cm) in smooth bodied Merino with wrinkly skin (53.4).

Fig.1, 2,3 and 4 Male weaner, female weaner, ram with ewes having high degree of skin folds

Growth traits: Scobie et al. (2005) reported higher body weight and fast growth rates in progeny of smooth sires than ribby rams. The plain-bodied animals have faster growth rates and higher lambing percentages (Olivier and Cloete 1998; Poggenpoel and van der Merwe 1987). Therefore, smooth sheep have improved total income of farmers (Londt and McMaster 1998).

Reproductive traits: Superior lambing performance of smooth ewes have been reported in past by researchers (Dun 1964; Dun and Hamilton 1965; Young et al. 1963; Drinan and Dun 1965; Fels 1964). Sheep with smooth skin generally have higher conception rates, twinning percentage and lower mortality among ewes and lambs (Atkins 1980; Rose 1976). Higher lambing and weaning percentages was found in ewes mated to smooth sires than Merino and Romney ewes mated to ribby sires (Scobie et al., 2005).

Fertility: Smooth rams having superior fertility and semen quality than rib rams. This may be attributed to improved ability of smooth sires to regulate their testis temperature (Fowler 1968; Fowler and Dun 1966; Fowler and Kennedy 1968; McGuirk 1969).

Heritability of skin wrinkles: Moderate heritability of 0.32, 0.39, and 0.45, was reported by Terrill and Hazel (1943), Terrill and Hazel (1946) and Jones et al. (1946), respectively for skin

wrinkles in sheep. Davis and McGuirk (1987) reviewed the heritability of wrinkles of 0.39. The genetic correlation between wool growth rate and wrinkles is poor (Davis and McGuirk. 1987). Undesirable correlations of skin wrinkle with other traits have also been observed plain-bodied animals, which have faster growth rates and higher lambing percentages (Olivier and Cloete 1998; Poggenpoel and van der Merwe 1987), and smooth sheep have been shown to improve total income (Londt and McMaster 1998). Similarly, Barlow (1974) observed that selection for clean fleece weight did not change the amount of skin wrinkle.

Carcass yield and dressing percentage: Dressing percentage or carcass yield is the proportion of ending live weight yielded after animals have been stunned (desensitized), exsanguinated, skinned or scalded and eviscerated (Casey and Webb., 2003). Carcass yield is expressed as the dressing percentage i.e dressed carcass weight/live weight $\times 100$ (Devine and Dikeman. 2014) The carcass yield is influenced by alimentary tract size and fill, slaughtering procedures, fleece mass, skin mass and size, distribution of body fat secondary sex characteristics, species, breed types and slaughtering procedures (Casey and Webb., 2003). As skin mass increase the carcass yield and dressing percentage will get reduced. Therefore, animal breeds having higher skin mass will result in lesser carcass yield and dressing percentage.

Conclusion

It is concluded that breeding Kashmir Merino for skin wrinkles as the trend is observed in farmers and breeders of Kashmir valley will dilute and deteriorate all production and reproduction traits. Higher skin fold have negative impact on wool and mutton traits. Higher skin fold have negative impact on wool, mutton, reproduction and carcass traits. The practice of breeding sheep for skin folds should be discouraged. Lambs with high degree of skin folds should be castrated at earlier age. Farmers should be encouraged and trained to bred sheep for growth traits.

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